

plasticheal

Types of data needed for tools
related to risk of MNP in CUSP and
beyond

DTU

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Purpose

- Explore whether some of the many nanorisk assessment frameworks can be used for human health risk assessment of MNPs?

Figure 21: Alternative decision-support tools or supplements to traditional risk assessment have been explored and proposed in recent years.

1) BSI 2007, 2) Paik et al. 2008, 3) Genaidy et al. 2009, 4) Zalk et al. 2009, 5) Ostiguy et al. 2010, 6) Groso et al. 2010, 7) Cornelissen et al. 2011, 8) Kristensen et al. 2010, Jensen et al. in prep. 9) van Duuren-Sturman et al. 2012, 10) Riediker et al. 2012, 11) Bouillard and Vignes 2014, 12) Gridelet et al. 2015, 13) Zalk and Paik 2016, 14) TÜV Süd 2008, 15) Bühler Partec (2010), 16) FOEN (2010), 17) Fransman et al. 2010, 18) Zuin et al. 2010, 19) Patel et al. 2013, 20) Hristozov et al. 2014, 21) Dekkers et al. 2016, 22) Shatkin and Kim 2015, 23) Shatkin 2008, 24) Shatkin 2009, 25) O'Brien and Cummins 2010 26) Davis 2007, 27) US EPA 2009, 28) US EPA 2010a, 29) US EPA 2010b, 30) Anastas and Davis 2011, 31) Howard and de Jong 2004, 32) Robichaud et al. 2005, 33) ED and Dupont 2007, 34) Hansen et al. 2007, 35) Hansen et al. 2008a, 36) Hansen et al. 2013a, 37) Hansen et al. 2014, 2017c, 38) Hjorth et al. 2017b, 39) SCENIHR 2005, 40) SCENIHR 2007, 41) Höck et al. 2008, 42) Sass et al. 2016, 43) Seager and Linkov 2008, 44) Tervonen et al. 2009, 45) Canis et al. 2010, 46) van Harmelen et al. 2015, 47) Linkov et al. 2007, 48) IRGC 2005, 49) IRGC 2007, 50) IRGC 2009, 51) Hansen and Baum 2015.

Information available wrt plastics?

- **Redox activity and/or catalytic activity**

- Available for plastics?
- Yes (e.g. Phenol–formaldehyde resin and PS (Chen et al., forthcoming, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fmre.2022.03.015>))

- **Stability in physiological and environmental conditions**

- Available for plastics?
- Yes (e.g. PE, PET, PLA (Chamas et al. 2020, <https://dx.doi.org/10.1021/acssuschemeng.9b06635>))

<https://www.bag.admin.ch/bag/en/home/gesund-leben/umwelt-und-gesundheit/chemikalien/nanotechnologie/sicherer-umgang-mit-nanomaterialien/vorsorgeraster-nanomaterialien-webanwendung.html>

ED & DuPont NanoRisk Framework

Hazard input information	Available for plastic?
Short-term tox	Yes - MP acute respiratory toxicity (Zhang et al., 2021), Cytotoxicity (Liang et al., 2021), Gastrointestinal toxicity (Jin et al., 2019; Qiao et al., 2019), NP Neurotoxicity Gambardella et al., 2018. NP Hepatotoxicity (Lusher et al., 2017)
Skin sensitization + penetration	
Genetic toxicity tests	Yes - MP Chronic immunotoxicity (Jin et al., 2019; H. Sun et al., 2021; M. Sun et al., 2021; T. Sun et al., 2021), NP Genotoxicity – Lusher et al., 2017
Biological fate + behavior	See figure of and next slide
Chronic inhalation/ingestion/dermal tox studies	Yes - MP Carcinogenicity – Martin et al., 2017, NP Nephrotoxicity (Gherkhbolagh et al., 2018) NP Cardiovascular toxicity (H. Sun et al., 2021; M. Sun et al., 2021; T. Sun et al., 2021), NP Hepatotoxicity (Lusher et al., 2017)
Developmental, reproductive, neuro and EDS- studies	Yes - MP Reproductive toxicity (Sobhani et al., 2021), Embryotoxicity (Uhrin and Schellinger, 2011), NP Reproductive toxicity (An et al., 2021)

Biological fate & behavior

Z. Yuan et al.

Science of the Total Environment 823 (2022) 153730

Fig. 3. Relationship between the fate of microplastics and nanoplastics in mammals and particle size.

What was no one looking at initially?

R. 7.1.3. Boiling point
R.7.1.5 Vapour pressure
R.7.1.6 Surface tension
R. 7.1.9 Flash point
R. 1.1.10 Flammability
R. 1.1.11 Physical properties
R. 1.1.12 Ignition temperature
R. 1.1.13 Granulometry
R. 1.1.17 Dissociation constant
R. 1.1.18 Viscosity

Basic properties

R. 7.2.2 Information requirements on skin corrosion/irritation
R. 7.2.3 Information sources on skin corrosion/irritation
R. 7.2.6 Testing and assessment strategy for skin corrosion/irritation
R. 7.2.7 Information requirements for serious eye damage/eye irritation
R. 7.2.8 Information sources on serious eye damage/eye irritation
R. 7.2.9 Evaluation of information on serious eye damage/eye irritation
R. 7.2.10 Conclusions on serious eye damage/eye irritation
R. 7.2.11 Testing and assessment strategy for serious eye damage/eye irritation
R. 7.2.12 Information requirements on respiratory tract corrosion/irritation
R. 7.2.13 Evaluation of information on respiratory tract corrosion/irritation
R. 7.3.2 Mechanisms of skin sensitisation
R. 7.3.3 Information requirements for skin sensitisation
R. 7.3.4 Information sources on skin sensitisation
R. 7.3.7 Testing and assessment strategy for skin sensitisation
R. 7.4.2 Non-testing data for acute toxicity
R.7.6.2 Information requirements on testing approaches for reproductive toxicity
R. 7.6.3 Information sources on reproductive toxicity
R. 7.6.4.2 Reproductive developmental toxicity screening test
R. 7.6.4.2 Prenatal developmental toxicity study
R. 7.6.4.2 Two-generation reproductive toxicity study
R. 7.6.7 Integrated Testing Strategy (ITS) for reproductive toxicity

Skin and Eyes

Reproductive tox

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R.8.1.2.3 Populations
R.8.1.2.7 Units
R.8.3 Step 2: Decide on mode of action (threshold or non-threshold) and which next step(s) to choose
R.8.5.2.1 The 'Linearised' approach
R.8.5.2.2 The 'Large Margin of Safety' approach ("EFSA")
R.8.5.2.3 Alternative to the conventional extrapolation procedures
R.8.5.3 Deriving a DMEL for a non-threshold carcinogen/mutagen, without adequate cancer data
R.8.6 Step 3-3: Follow a more qualitative approach when no dose descriptor is available for an endpoint
R.8.7.1 Selection of the critical DN(M)EL
R.8.7.2 Endpoints for which no DNEL/DMEL can be derived
R.8.7.3 Using DN(M)EL for human exposure patterns

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Regulatory reliability and relevance of academic data

- Ensuring regulatory reliability and relevance of data produced in PlasticHeal
- Use of SciRAP evaluation criteria
 - SciRAP: Science in Risk Assessment and Policy
 - Webbased platform (www.scirap.org)
- Aim to *”bridge the gap between academic research and chemical regulation and policy”*
- Molander et al. (2015) presented SciRAP as:
”a framework that facilitates a systematic and transparent evaluation of the reliability and relevance of (eco)toxicity in vivo studies for health and environmental risk assessment”

The screenshot shows the homepage of the Science in Risk Assessment and Policy (SciRAP) website. The header is black with the title in green. A navigation menu includes links for Start, About, Videos, In vivo toxicity, In vitro toxicity, Ecotoxicity, and Publications. The main heading is 'Science in Risk Assessment and Policy'. Below this is a paragraph describing SciRAP as a web-based reporting and evaluation resource. A section titled 'Why is this important?' discusses the need for structure and transparency in regulatory risk assessment. Another section, 'Intended use?', describes the resource for regulators, risk assessors, and researchers. At the bottom, it mentions a collaboration between Stockholm University and Karolinska Institutet, with logos for both institutions.

Science in Risk Assessment and Policy

Start About Videos In vivo toxicity In vitro toxicity Ecotoxicity Publications

Science in Risk Assessment and Policy

SciRAP (Science in Risk Assessment and Policy) is a web-based reporting and evaluation resource developed to facilitate and increase the use of academic toxicity and ecotoxicity studies in regulatory assessment of chemicals. The intention is to bridge the gap between academic research and chemicals regulation and policy.

Why is this important? There is overall a need to increase structure and transparency in the evaluation of (eco)toxicity studies for regulatory risk assessment of chemicals. Further, academic research studies are often given little weight as evidence in risk assessment. One reason is that they are considered insufficiently reported for regulatory purposes.

Intended use? The SciRAP resource is intended for regulators and risk assessors as well as researchers, reviewers and editors. SciRAP provides criteria for the evaluation of reliability and relevance of studies intended for **regulators and risk assessors**. The reporting guidelines are intended as a tool for **researchers** in the design, performance, and reporting of studies. The criteria presented here can also be used as a template in the **review process** for scientific publication to increase the reliability and reproducibility of studies.

SciRAP is a collaboration between the [Department of Environmental Science \(ACES\)](#), Stockholm University, and the [Institute of Environmental Medicine \(IMM\)](#), Karolinska Institutet. Please [contact us](#) if you have questions or comments.

 Karolinska Institutet

Task 7.3 Ensuring Policy Relevance - SciRAP evaluation of studies

- Example of application of SciRAP reporting criteria
 - Domenech et al. 2021
- Aim :
 - For all our papers
 - WP7 in collaboration with authors

Article

Polystyrene Nanoplastics as Carriers of Metals. Interactions of Polystyrene Nanoparticles with Silver Nanoparticles and Silver Nitrate, and Their Effects on Human Intestinal Caco-2 Cells

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Abstract: Environmental plastic wastes are continuously degraded to their micro and nanoforms. Since in the environment they coexist with other pollutants, it has been suggested that they could act as vectors transporting different toxic trace elements, such as metals. To confirm this, we have

Evaluation criteria	Selection
Test compound and controls	
1. The chemical name or other identification, such as CAS-number, of the test compound was given.	Fulfilled
2. The purity of the test compound was stated or is traceable according to information given regarding manufacturer and lot/batch number. In case of mixtures, the composition of different	Partially fulfilled
3. The solubility of the test compound was described.	Fulfilled
4. The solvent (vehicle) was described.	Fulfilled
5. It was stated that a solvent (vehicle) control was included.	Fulfilled
Test System	
6. The test system (e.g., cell line / cell / tissue / organ / embryo / sub-cellular fractions) was described.	Fulfilled
7. The source of the test system was stated.	Fulfilled
8. The metabolic competence, i.e., competence of the test system to metabolize the test compound into an active metabolite was	Not determined
9. The number of cell passages of the cell line used, was stated. (Remove this criterion if the study was not conducted in a cell line.)	Fulfilled
10. Composition of media was described, including use of serum, antibiotics, etc.	Fulfilled
11. Incubation temperature, humidity, and CO2 concentration were described.	Fulfilled
12. Measures taken for avoiding or screening for contamination by mycoplasma, bacteria, fungi and virus were described.	Partially fulfilled
Administration of test compound	
13. The administered dose levels or concentrations were stated.	Fulfilled
14. Cell density or number of cells used during treatment was described.	Fulfilled
15. The duration of treatment was stated.	Fulfilled
16. The number of replicates per dose level/concentration or the number of times the experiment was repeated was stated.	Fulfilled
Data collection and analysis	
17. The tests and/or analytical methods used were sufficiently described to allow for evaluation of reliability of results.	Fulfilled
18. The time points for data collection were stated.	Partially fulfilled
19. It was stated that the effect of the test compound on cytotoxicity was measured.	Fulfilled
20. All results were clearly presented.	Fulfilled
21. The statistical methods and software used were described.	Fulfilled
Funding and competing interests	
22. The funding sources for the study were stated.	Fulfilled
23. Any competing interests were disclosed or it was explicitly stated that the authors did not have any competing interests.	Fulfilled
Other	
24. Was all information that is indispensable for evaluating the reliability of data given? This includes information on the test compound and controls, test system, study design or study	

Conclusion

- Several tools and frameworks that could be used to assess risks of MNPs
- Information is available for many of the input parameters needed to use these
- Information is not always available for all MNPs and their additives
- Not clear whether the final end results of the tools and framework captures the essence of MNPs risks

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Thank you
for your attention!

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